

THE HERO WITHIN: PSYCHOLOGICAL CAPITAL AND WORK ENGAGEMENT, A STUDY AMONG TEACHERS

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Abstract

Teacher engagement is a critical factor in educational success, influencing both teacher well-being and student outcomes. This study examines the influence of Psychological Capital (PsyCap) on teacher engagement. Using a sample of 405 teachers, we conducted correlation and regression analysis to explore the relationships between these variables. The findings indicate that PsyCap (hope, efficacy, resilience, and optimism) has a significant positive impact on teacher engagement, suggesting that teachers with higher psychological resources are more likely to be engaged. These results underscore the importance of fostering psychological resources, resilience, and a sense of purpose in teachers to enhance engagement levels. The study provides practical implications for educational policymakers and administrators, advocating for professional development programs that nurture psychological strength and promote meaning in teaching.

Keywords: *Psychological Capital HERO, Teacher Engagement, NEP-2020, Education, Motivation,*

Introduction:

Teachers have vital responsibilities in achieving educational goals and raising future generations. In meeting social expectations regarding education, teachers are expected to keep their motivation alive and dedicate themselves to their work (İlğan & Ceviz, 2019; Somech & Ron, 2007). When teachers develop positive attitudes towards their profession, they can transfer all their energies to their work (Granziera & Perera, 2019). The **National Education Policy (NEP) 2020** of India emphasizes the importance of teacher engagement and the need

for a comprehensive approach to improving the quality of teaching. It recognizes that teachers are central to the educational process and their active involvement is the key to the success of any educational system. The NEP 2020 underscores the importance of teacher engagement through empowerment, professional development, autonomy, and fostering a collaborative and creative teaching environment. Teachers are seen as critical agents of change in the education system and are central to shaping the future of students.

In this context, job engagement, which requires transferring physical, mental, and emotional energy to the work roles (Kahn, 1990), comes to the fore for teachers. “Teacher engagement: is a motivational construct reflecting the voluntary allocation of teachers’ resources and energy across teaching-related activities (Klassen et al., 2012). Teacher engagement is a way of describing work engagement that is specific to teachers in a classroom setting.

Given these high expectations, teaching often leads to burnout, with negative consequences on mental health and job retention which ultimately lead to disengagement. However, these undesirable outcomes may be mitigated, among other things, by a teacher’s job satisfaction, grit, meaningful work and personal resources, such as psychological capital (PsyCap) (Adil and Kamal 2023; Mikus and Teoh 2022).

Theoretical Frame work

Positive psychology has been described in many ways and with many words, but the commonly accepted definition of the field is this: “Positive psychology is the scientific study of what makes life most worth living” (Peterson, 2008). To push this brief description a bit further, positive psychology is a scientific approach to studying human thoughts, feelings, and behavior, with a focus on strengths instead of weaknesses, building the good in life instead of repairing the bad, and taking the lives of average people up to “great” instead of focusing solely on moving those who are struggling up to “normal” (Peterson, 2008).

Rationale of the Study

Work engagement plays a vital role in improved interpersonal relationships amongst employees, which in turn fosters better performance. Together with improved interpersonal relations, work engagement is expected to foster a proactive attitude amongst employees which will ultimately lead to better performance. The reason why work engagement is of such interest to our study is that it is not just a matter of simple satisfaction with work or at work, loyalty to company or employer, but it is way beyond, as the employees who are engaged are passionate and so committed that they almost invest themselves to help the organization in this case the school and education system to succeed.

Another interesting fact about work engagement is that it fosters happiness and work enjoyableness, where it is not an external reward, but employees tend to work more toward their internal satisfaction by looking at the tasks positively even when they are expected to face strain.

Therefore the purpose of this study is to understand the influence of psychological capital, which fosters work engagement with happiness and work enjoyableness to achieve more inclusive and equitable quality education as envisaged in NEP2020.

Research Gap

Most studies focus on western contexts leaving gaps in studies in Indian background and how psychological capital influences the work engagement of teachers.

There is limited research on psychological capital in developing countries.

While, psychological capital is widely studied in corporate settings, fewer studies explore psychological capital development programmes for teachers

Thus, the above gaps from the reviewed studies can be filled through the present research on psychological capital and its effect on work engagement.

Objectives of the study

1. To examine the Psychological Capital of teachers in relation to their teacher engagement

Hypothesis of the study

H1: Psychological capital of teachers is positively related to teacher engagement

Research Methodology

The main aim of the study is to study the effect of positive psychological capital, on work engagement of teachers. In order to study the effect of psychological capital, work on teacher engagement, using data collection 1. Psychological capital measurement scale by Luthans et al 2. Engaged Teacher Scale (ETS) Klassen et al, a sample of 405 high school teachers working in the Local body institutions below the age group 61 are chosen for data collection.

Data Analysis and Interpretation

The collected data is analyzed by the objectives and hypotheses accordingly selected sample and sample characteristics and sampling distribution.. The data was analyzed based on the demographic variables.

Categorical variables were analyzed using frequencies. The dataset comprises 405 respondents with a nearly equal distribution of gender, where 51.6% (n = 209) are male and 48.4% (n = 196) are female. Concerning degrees held by the participants, 81.2% have either a master's degree, while 18.8% hold a bachelor's degree. Regarding the kind of professional qualifications

held by the participants, 84.7% have a Bachelor of Education (B.Ed.), and 15.3% have a Master of Education (M.Ed.). For the kind of work experience held by the respondents, 81.0% have more than 14 years of experience, followed by 13.6% between 10 and 14 years, 3.0% between 1.1 and 4 years and 2.5% between 2.5 and 9 years of experience. For job positions, 89.4% of the groups hold the position of SA, and 10.6% hold the position of SGT. Most of the teachers belonged to married category 95.3%, 0.5% divorced, single are 1.7% and widowed are 2.5%. Looking at the kind of locations where participants work, 56.5% work in rural areas while 43.5% work in urban areas. Employment status data shows that 100% of participants are employed permanently. Finally, in terms of marital status, 95.3% of the participants are married.

The participants' age ranges from 32 to 61 years. 11.9% teachers are from 30-40 age group, highest number with a percentage of 48.6% of teachers belonged to 40-50. the age group 50-61 were 39.5%. In the category of marital status, Out of the 405 teachers 386 are married, that is 95.3%. 0.5% are divorced. 1.7% are single and 2.5% are widowed.

Results and Findings

In order to carry out further analysis and interpretation, the collected data was screened and was finalized for data analysis. The SPSSV.27 was used for the data analysis. The data was analyzed based on the demographic variables. The correlations and regression results are elaborated and the findings are presented further.

Objective1. To examine the Psychological Capital of teachers in relation to their teacher engagement

In order to understand the impact and influence of psychological capital on teacher engagement the data was subjected to inferential statistics. A Pearson correlation coefficient and multiple regression analysis was carried out and results are presented in the table 1 given below.

Table 1

The Pearson correlation coefficients among various psychological capital (PSYCAP) components and Total Teacher Engagement Scale (TE) dimensions

variables	Me	S	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
1. Psychological Capital	127.48	8.79	1									

2.Hope	30.10	5.87	.934**									
3. Efficacy	33.71	1.35	.826**	.784**								
4. Resilience	31.94	2.01	.794**	.554**	.523**							
5Optimism	31.71	1.38	.426**	.112**	.181**	.723**						
6.Teacher Engagement (Total)	87.79	17.5	.708**	.579**	.634**	.560**	.605**					
7. Emotional Engagement	22.47	4.89	.616**	.455**	.581**	.545**	.625**	.984**				
8.CognitiveEngagement	22.86	4.16	.629**	.524**	.708**	.421**	.468**	.963**	.963**			
9. Social Engagement(colleagues)	21.60	5.02	.712**	.644**	.545**	.530**	.483**	.958**	.925**	.884**		
10. Social Engagement(students)	20.84	4.17	.769**	.603**	.621**	.657**	.761**	.935**	.891**	.858**	.856**	1

When it comes to Psychological Capital and its influence on Teacher Engagement it is found .708, which means a strong positive correlation indicates that individuals with higher psychological capital tend to have greater overall engagement.

These correlations suggest that hopeful and resilient individuals are more likely to engage fully in tasks. Optimism has a moderate positive correlation with engagement, indicating that optimistic individuals tend to be more engaged.

Table 2

Multiple Regression Analysis of the Criterion Variable (Teacher Engagement)
Multiple Regression Analysis Results: psychological capital explaining the Criterion Variable (Teacher Engagement)

Variable	F	df	Adj.R ²	β	sig
Dependent variable(Teacher Engagement)	202.678	404	.500		
Location				.025	.486
Psychological capital				.708	<.001

This table presents the results of a multiple linear regression analysis, examining the influence of Location and Psychological Capital on Teacher Engagement (dependent variable). The high F-value (202.678) indicates that the regression model is statistically significant. Adjusted R² = 0.500 explains 50% of the variance in teacher engagement. The relationship between location and teacher engagement is ($\beta = 0.025$, $p = 0.456$) weak and statistically insignificant ($p > 0.05$). Location does not play a meaningful role in determining teacher engagement. The results suggest that where a teacher works (urban/rural, school type, etc.) does not significantly influence engagement.

The positive β value (0.708) indicates that higher psychological capital leads to greater teacher engagement. The relationship is statistically significant ($p < 0.001$), confirming the strong impact of psychological capital.

Thus, the correlation and regression analysis supports the hypothesis, that there is a strong positive correlation between psychological capital and teacher engagement and location does not have any effect on teacher engagement and can be controlled and confounded

Findings

1. There is positive significant relation confirmed in the study between the Psychological Capital of teachers in relation to their teacher engagement
2. There is found no impact of location on teacher engagement, hence location is confounded.

Conclusion

To conclude, the findings of this study focus on the importance of psychological capital. The results lead to stressing on the importance of Positive Resources like hope and resilience should be encouraged in teachers and students as they will increase, Provide opportunities to encourage teachers with self-efficacy in order to handle tough situations with autonomy. Policy

makers should encourage teachers to take ownership of their work. It is emphasized that being empathetic towards colleagues and students should be encouraged. Teachers should be encouraged to develop coping mechanisms to handle stressful situations and be encouraged to create positive work environment. Design the programmes to train in positive psychological resources through training programs, workshops and counseling sessions .Implementing mentorship programs can boost self-efficacy and resilience among teachers as envisaged in the NEP-2020

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